

Economics and Business Quarterly Reviews

Anh, N. T. V., & Hoang, P. M. (2023). Motivating Factors and Online Behavior Influencing the Choice of Community-Based Tourism Preferences of Generation Z in Vietnam. *Economics and Business Quarterly Reviews*, 6(4), 39-55.

ISSN 2775-9237

DOI: 10.31014/aior.1992.06.04.538

The online version of this article can be found at:
<https://www.asianinstituteofresearch.org/>

Published by:
The Asian Institute of Research

The *Economics and Business Quarterly Reviews* is an Open Access publication. It may be read, copied, and distributed free of charge according to the conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

The Asian Institute of Research *Economics and Business Quarterly Reviews* is a peer-reviewed International Journal. The journal covers scholarly articles in the fields of Economics and Business, which includes, but is not limited to, Business Economics (Micro and Macro), Finance, Management, Marketing, Business Law, Entrepreneurship, Behavioral and Health Economics, Government Taxation and Regulations, Financial Markets, International Economics, Investment, and Economic Development. As the journal is Open Access, it ensures high visibility and the increase of citations for all research articles published. The *Economics and Business Quarterly Reviews* aims to facilitate scholarly work on recent theoretical and practical aspects of Economics and Business.

ASIAN INSTITUTE OF RESEARCH
Connecting Scholars Worldwide

Motivating Factors and Online Behavior Influencing the Choice of Community-Based Tourism Preferences of Generation Z in Vietnam

Nguyen Thi Van Anh¹, Pham Minh Hoang²

¹ University of Labor and Social Affairs. Email: nguyenvananh83@ulsa.edu.vn

² Le Quy Don High School for the Gifted, Da Nang. Email: hoangpham06.forwork@gmail.com

Abstract

The research examines the motivations for community-based tourism with four types, including "Learning," "Spending time with family," "Nature," and "Experience - Exploration." The investigation involved scrutinizing each statement using Likert 5-scale questions. Among the four motivations for Gen Z in Vietnam participating in this type of tourism, the "Enjoying nature" motivation has the highest average score of 4.22 and is the only one that reached the threshold of "Strongly Agree." For those young people who intend to engage in community-based tourism, similar to those who have already participated, the "Enjoying nature" motivation has the highest average score, with 4.15 points. The group that has already participated shows a significant difference in the data regarding the level of online behavior before participating in tourism. Concerning the travel behavior of "Reading travel reviews on social media," it is the most commonly performed activity, with 95.65% in the group that has participated and 9.259% in the group with the intention to participate.

Keywords: Motivations, Online Behavior, Decision-Making, Community-Based Tourism Preferences, Young People, Gen Z, Vietnam

1. Raising the Issues

According to the Vietnam National Tourism Administration (2019), *community-based* tourism is defined as an activity in which a community's population participates in tourism. Currently, community-based tourism is considered the most sustainable form of tourism that brings economic development benefits to local residents. Community-based tourism not only helps people protect ecological resources but also preserves and promotes the unique cultural aspects of the locality. Vietnam has great potential in terms of natural landscapes, historical and cultural values of ethnic communities, customs and ways of life, and diverse culinary culture in various regions, providing a strong foundation for the development of community-based tourism (Doan Manh Cuong, 2019).

Community-based tourism is increasingly attracting many tourists due to its intimate and authentic nature. It includes various forms depending on factors such as topography, historical length, and natural scenery.

This study aims to understand the motivations of Gen Z young people (1997-2012) who intend to or have chosen community-based tourism and their online behaviors before, during, and after their participation in community-

based tourism. The research team conducted an examination of the concept of community-based tourism, various types of community-based tourism, an overview of tourism studies, community-based tourism, and travel motivations, as well as studies related to online behaviors in tourism in general and community-based tourism in particular. By analyzing and synthesizing these findings in combination with survey results from 336 young people, including 230 who have participated in community-based tourism (69%), 81 who intend to do so (24%), and 25 who do not plan to (7%), the research team examined online behaviors before, during, and after trips for the young people who have engaged in community-based tourism, as well as behaviors before trips for the young people who have not yet traveled but plan to do so in the near future. This allowed for a comparative analysis between the two groups. Additionally, the study investigated the motivations for community-based tourism, categorizing them into four types: 'Learning,' 'Spending time with family,' 'Nature,' and 'Experience - Exploration.' Each motivation was assessed using Likert 5-scale questions to calculate the average value of each motivation, enabling a comparison between the two surveyed groups to identify similarities and differences in travel motivations

2. Theoretical Basis

2.1. Community-based tourism

2.1.1. Community-based tourism

Community-based tourism is regarded as a type of tourism that attracts many visitors due to its close and authentic nature. When tourists engage in community-based tourism, they are invited to villages and areas where local residents live. Here, they are provided with accommodation and have the opportunity to enjoy local, traditional dishes and specialties. Additionally, tourists experience the daily lives of local residents, allowing them to explore and learn about the cultural and traditional values of the region. The expenses incurred by tourists contribute to the income of local communities, ultimately leading to various sustainable economic development benefits for the area (Dinh Thuy Dung, 2022).

According to Article 15, Clause 3 of the 2017 Tourism Law: *Community-based tourism is a type of tourism developed based on the cultural values of the community. It is managed, organized, exploited, and benefited from by the local community.*

Community-based tourism is a type of tourism that involves the participation of the local community in the supply chain and management of tourism. This tourism model is established and developed based on the community's own culture, managed, organized and benefited by the local community (Vinpearl, 2021).

Therefore, we can understand that *community-based tourism is an activity in which a local community engages in tourism. In other words, it is a type of tourism in which the local community participates in the supply chain and management of tourism. This form of tourism is developed based on the community's culture and is managed, organized and benefited by the local community.*

2.1.2. Types of community-based tourism

Community-based tourism is a highly diverse tourism model that encompasses various types depending on factors such as geographical terrain, historical length, and natural landscapes. According to Hoteljob.vn (2021), some common forms of community-based tourism include:

Ecotourism: This type of community-based tourism takes place in areas with suitable conditions. Tourists visit these areas to explore the beauty of the local culture and social life while being environmentally conscious.

Cultural Tourism: Cultural community-based tourism is based on the local culture, history, and archaeology of the area to create unique and attractive tourism products.

Agricultural Tourism: This form of community-based tourism allows visitors to experience life in the local agricultural areas, such as animal farms, combined agriculture and forestry farms, fruit orchards, vegetable gardens. Visitors can both tour and engage in local farming activities.

Indigenous Tourism: Indigenous community-based tourism directly involves local indigenous people and minority ethnic communities in tourism activities to attract and serve tourists.

Village Tourism: Village community-based tourism is a type where rural villages in the area create economic benefits through tourism. They attract tourists by sharing the activities of rural life and providing services related to food, accommodation, and entertainment for those interested.

Arts and Crafts: This type of community-based tourism is particularly well-developed in areas with a long history. It combines tourism with hands-on activities to create beautiful art or handicraft products.

2.2. Travel motivation

The concept of travel motivation is used to refer to a collection of attributes that play the role of causes for a person to engage in a travel activity (Li M, Zhang H, Xiao H, Chen Y, 2015). It also explains the behavior of tourists because it forms the motivations and attractions behind each type of behavior (Crompton JL, 1979). Travel motivation is directly related to the reason why a person decides to engage in travel activities (Chen CF, Chen FS, 2010).

Travel motivation is the reason for the act of traveling in order to satisfy the needs and desires of tourists. It is a subjective factor that encourages people to turn their travel needs into actual actions. Furthermore, travel motivation indicates the psychological reasons that encourage individuals to travel, choose a destination, and engage in a particular type of travel (Mai TT, et al, 2013)

Travel motivation is considered a key factor in explaining the behavior of tourists. Dann G., (1977) argued that these motivations include both push and pull factors that drive individuals to engage in travel behavior. Push motivations are factors that stimulate or create desires within the tourist (Uysal M, Hagan LR, 1993; Crompton, 1979). Push factors include escaping from routine life, relaxation, demonstrating status, physical health and fitness, adventure, social interaction, spending time with family, and seeking enjoyment (Crompton, 1979). Pull motivations are generated from external influences (Yoon Y, Uysal M, 2005), related to situational and perceptual inspiration through various objective factors, such as the attractiveness of the destination (Yoon Y, Uysal M, 2005). Pull motivations are primarily studied in relation to tangible resources that determine the attractiveness of a destination (Kim S, Lee C, & Klenosky D, 2003), natural and historical attractions, cuisine, people (Ha T.T.T, et al, 2019), supporting technological means, entertainment, and destination image promotion.

In contrast to extrinsic motivation, intrinsic motivation is the drive for performing actions that inherently provide satisfaction or enjoyment without being influenced by external factors (Legault, 2016). Travel motivation is part of consumer motivation, which includes both extrinsic and intrinsic motivation, driving consumer purchasing and service use behavior. In tourism studies, motivation is a crucial factor as it determines supply and demand in the tourism service market (Fields, 2002; Mahika, 2011; Johnson & Thomas 1992)."

Regarding intrinsic motivation driving travel intentions and decisions, experimental studies have yielded different results from various perspectives. Beard & Ragheb (1983) proposed a model called Ragheb LMS based on Maslow's hierarchy of needs and divided travel motivation factors into four components as follows: (i) Cognitive component: learning and exploration activities; (ii) Social component: the need for social relationships and the need for respect from others; (iii) Skill-related component: determining how individuals engage in recreational activities to achieve accomplishments, leadership, and competition; these activities are often physical in nature; (iv) Avoidance component: identifying the need for escape from life's stressors, including avoiding social interaction, seeking independence, tranquility, and relaxation.

Mahika (2011) suggests that travel motivations are to some extent influenced by individual characteristics of the travelers, which include: (i) Personality traits; (ii) Lifestyle of the individual; (iii) Past experiences, both positive and negative; (iv) The individual's past (nostalgia for specific places); (v) Perspective or viewpoints of the individual; (vi) Socioeconomic status. A study by Pham Quoc Tri & Trinh Thi Thu (2021) on factors influencing the decision to choose rural tourism destinations based on community engagement in the North Central region of Vietnam proposed a model that includes two primary categories: (1) internal factors, and (2) external factors. The internal factors consist of four intrinsic motivations, namely (1) the desire for exploration, (2) the desire for relaxation, (3) the desire for social interaction, and (4) economic motivation, with the desire for social interaction and relaxation having the most significant impact. Smith et al., (2020) conducted a study on motivations, experiences, and demographics of cultural tourists, an essential component of community-based tourism, in Budapest. They identified seven key cultural tourism experiences. The statistical analysis of 614 responses received from tourists in Budapest in April 2019, spanning various age groups (from 18 to over 74), nationalities (including the UK, France, Germany, Italy, and Spain), and genders (52% female and 48% male), revealed that almost every age group rated two experiences, 'enjoying the atmosphere' and 'enjoying food and drinks,' with an average score above 6 on the Likert scale. A study by Hanh et al., (2021) on student satisfaction with community-based tourism activities in Hoa Vang District, Da Nang, measured student motivations in participating in these activities. It identified three extrinsic motivations and one intrinsic motivation: 'Having a personal desire to engage in educational and experiential travel.' The study yielded an average score of 4.1525 for this motivation, the highest among the four motivations measured. Chanapong Arpornpisal (2018) identified four driving motivations for travel behavior.

Jutamas Phengkona and Paithoon Monpanthong (2022) conducted a study to classify domestic tourists visiting community-based tourism destinations in Thailand based on their motivations. The research used quantitative research as the primary research method to achieve its objectives. A self-administered online survey was conducted with 384 tourists, and the primary data was analyzed using cluster analysis. The study identified three clusters of tourists, which included "learning tourists," "entertainment tourists," and "multi-purpose tourists." These tourist groups differed in terms of their travel motivations, with four types of motivations taken into consideration: "Learning," "Spending time with family," "Nature," and "Experiencing and Exploring." Additionally, social demographic profiles and online behaviors were also considered. The results of the study provide significant insights for scholars and practitioners, allowing them to understand the differences between tourist groups and develop more tailored marketing strategies for community-based tourism destinations based on each customer segment. Furthermore, there were notable differences between the three tourist groups concerning age and gender.

2.3. Online travel behavior

In recent years, the global travel trend has shifted towards unique travel experiences that contribute to the sustainable development of the tourism industry. Furthermore, the combination of travel with information technology is a notable trend, enhancing the customer experience and creating new opportunities for the tourism sector. Online travel businesses will need to update and offer products and services that meet these needs to attract customers. Customers are seeking convenience, flexibility, and cost savings in booking hotels, flights, tours, and other services. This presents an opportunity for online travel businesses to develop suitable products and services to attract customers (Ngo Thai Hoang Tuan, 2023).

As the behavior of travelers is gradually changing, instead of going to local agencies, they are now booking tours directly on travel company websites. According to the World Tourism Organization, tourists have entered a new phase known as connected tourism. In this phase, travelers actively seek destinations, tours, hotels, book flights, and related services. Travelers also proactively post comments and reviews about hotels, tours, and the quality of services during their journeys. These reviews are often considered more trustworthy than information from professional travel surveying and rating agencies (Thanh Giang, 2019).

According to the Vietnam E-Commerce Association (VECOM), global online travel agency (OTA) brands such as Agoda.com, Booking.com, Traveloka.com, Expedia.com (including Trivago.com, Hotel.com) hold up to 80% of the market share in Vietnam. Technology platforms have significantly contributed to the development of the

tourism industry. All travel companies aim to have the best tools to help customers find products and services quickly. However, travel experts emphasize that conducting online travel is not just about creating a website or a mobile app; it's also about effectively and conveniently attracting customers to use their products (Thanh Giang, 2019).

According to Nguyen Thi Hong Ngoc (2017), online reviews have become one of the information channels that travelers use when making their choices. Applying a model of the factors affecting travelers' decisions based on opinions from tourists, the author analyzed the impact of online reviews on hotel choices in Hue. The research results proposed a model assessing the influence of online reviews on hotel selection decisions. This implies that the management and development of information channels based on online reviews by hotels need to focus on improving customer care activities, providing information, meeting, and supporting travelers when they visit Hue.

In their 2022 study, Jutamas Phengkona and Paithoon Monpanthong examined the online travel behavior of three groups of customers: "learning-oriented tourists," "entertainment-oriented tourists," and "multi-purpose tourists." They investigated the behavior of these groups before, during, and after their community-based travel experiences. When planning a trip, most tourists read travel reviews from social media, which was the highest proportion of tourists compared to other clusters. Discussion boards were also used as sources for travel reviews of tourists in this cluster. They received travel information and promotion through emails more than other clusters. They mainly searched for travel information via destination websites and search engines. Contacting service providers, reserving tourism products and services as well as checking the status of location, weather, or traffic through websites were other online activities performed by the tourists before taking a trip. While traveling, they shared travel experience on social media, checked-in at destinations, live broadcasted showing their experience, and searched for more travel information in the nearby locations. After the trip, tourists also continued posting travel experiences on social media and sharing video clips on YouTube. It was notable that the tourists in this cluster were more interested in writing travel reviews on destination websites, blogs, review websites, and discussion boards more than other clusters. These showed that most tourists in this cluster were more active in using online while traveling and after returning home from a trip than those tourists of other clusters.

3. Research Methodology

3.1. Data collection method:

To investigate "*Motivating factors and online behavior influencing the choice of community-based tourism preferences of Generation Z young people in Vietnam*", the research team employed two research methods: desk research (reviewing published materials through various media) and sociological surveys (collecting responses from Gen Z young people in Vietnam). The collected data will be aggregated and analyzed using Excel and SPSS software.

Through the desk research method, the research team examined literature on community-based tourism destinations, various forms of community-based tourism, and articles related to motivations and behaviors in tourism in general and community-based tourism in particular. This was done using academic databases such as Researchgate, Scien Direct, IEE Explore, Scopus, Emerald, Insight, Taylor & Francis Online, in addition to the Google Scholar search tool and various travel and community-based tourism information websites. Subsequently, the research team developed a survey questionnaire to conduct a sociological investigation into the motivational and online behavior factors that influence the choice of community-based tourism among Gen Z young people in Vietnam.

For the sociological survey, the research team conducted preliminary surveys and discussions with Gen Z tourists in Vietnam who have shown interest in and have visited community-based tourism destinations. These discussions used a preliminary measurement scale concerning motivational and online behavioral factors specific to community-based tourism, following the approach outlined by Jutamas Phengkona & Paithoon Monpanthong (2022). Participants in the discussions were encouraged to provide their opinions on relevant aspects to enhance the survey questionnaire. The preliminary research sample consisted of 10 individuals. The findings from this

preliminary research were used to refine the research questionnaire. After finalizing the survey questionnaire, the research team distributed and collected responses via the Google Form link (https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSepkjrKCFcE-PuELITpz_VnL6bw3XXhS0kouNeebjkIP6Xobg/viewform) from Gen Z young people in Vietnam.

Data collection methods employed a convenience sampling approach and the snowball sampling method (finding the next subjects based on recommendations or introductions from those who participated in the initial survey) to ensure an adequate sample size. A total of 336 survey responses were collected, with 311 respondents indicating that they had traveled to community-based tourism destinations and intended to select this type of tourism.

3.2. Data processing method:

The research team used a Likert 5-scale when constructing the survey questionnaire for motivational questions, where: 1. Strongly Disagree; 2. Disagree; 3. Neutral; 4. Agree; 5. Strongly Agree. To assess the impact level of each factor, the team calculated the range and average value of each factor and determined the average score within which response categories it falls.

$$\text{Range Value} = (\text{Maximum} - \text{Minimum}) / n = (5-1) / 5 = 0.8$$

The assessment categories based on average score values are as follows:

- + 1.00 - 1.80: Strongly Disagree
- + 1.81 - 2.60: Disagree
- + 2.61 - 3.40: Neutral
- + 3.41 - 4.20: Agree
- + 4.21 - 5.00: Strongly Agree

For questions related to online behavior, the questions were designed to assess whether Gen Z young people in Vietnam "Yes" or "No" engage in specific behaviors. This helped identify which behaviors are frequently practiced and which are less common among these young individuals, serving as a basis for discussions and exchanges with community-based tourism professionals, particularly in the context of community-based tourism.

4. Survey Results of Motivating Factors and Online Behavior of Gen Z Young People in Vietnam about Community-Based Tourism

4.1. Descriptive statistics of survey participants

Figure 1: Gender of survey participants

Source: Survey results

Participating in the survey were 336 young individuals, including 69 males (21%), 260 females (77%), and 7 who preferred not to specify (2%).

Figure 2: Survey participants' age

Source: Survey results

Participating in the survey were 336 young individuals, including 54 born in 1997-2002 (16%), 273 born in 2003-2007 (81%), and 9 born in 2008-2012 (3%).

Figure 3: Percentage of Survey Participants Engaging in Community-Based Tourism

Source: Survey results

Participating in the survey were 336 young individuals, of which 230 had previously engaged in community-based tourism (69%), 81 had not but intended to (24%), and 25 had not and had no intention to do so (7%).

4.2. Online Behavior

4.2.1. For the group that had engaged in community-based tourism

Table 1: Online Behavior Before Engaging in Community-based Tourism
(For those who had experienced community-based tourism)

	Yes		No	
	People	%	People	%
Reading travel reviews on social media	220	95.65	10	4.35
Reading travel reviews on online forums	188	81.74	42	18.26

Reading travel reviews from blogs	189	82.17	41	17.83
Reading travel reviews from review websites	176	76.52	52	22.61
Searching for travel information on destination websites	202	87.83	28	12.17
Using search engines to find travel information	210	91.30	20	8.70
Asking or messaging acquaintances and friends about the destination	200	86.96	30	13.04
Contacting service providers	162	70.43	68	29.57
Pre-booking travel products and services	183	79.57	47	20.43
Checking location/weather/traffic information on websites	204	88.70	26	11.30
Searching for travel information from travel agency websites	158	68.70	72	31.30
Receiving travel information and promotions through email	105	45.65	125	54.35
Creating travel-related topics on forums	91	39.57	139	60.43

Source: Survey results

Regarding online behavior before participating in community-based tourism, for the group of young people who have previously engaged in this type of tourism, it is evident that "Reading travel reviews on social media" and "Searching for travel information on search engines" are the two most common online behaviors, with 95.65% and 91.30% of survey participants, respectively, reporting that they performed these activities. Conversely, "Receiving travel information and promotions through email" and "Creating travel-related topics on forums" are the two least commonly practiced online behaviors, with only 54.35% and 60.45% of participants, respectively, indicating their involvement.

Table 2: Online Behavior While Participating in Community-Based Tourism
(For those who had experienced community-based tourism)

	Yes		No	
	People	%	People	%
Posting images/videos on social media	186	80.87	44	19.13
Checking in at various locations	204	88.70	26	11.30
Searching for travel products and services within the vicinity	205	89.13	25	10.87
Making advance bookings for travel products and services	158	68.70	72	31.30
Livestreaming travel products and services	46	20.00	184	80.00

Checking location/weather/traffic on the web	207	90.00	23	10.00
--	-----	-------	----	-------

Source: Survey results

In terms of online behavior while participating in community-based tourism, the group of young people who had previously engaged in this type of travel demonstrated that 'Checking location/weather/traffic on the web' and 'Searching for travel products and services within the vicinity' were the most common online behaviors, with 90.00% and 89.13% of respondents indicating that they engaged in these activities. 'Livestreaming travel products and services' was the least frequently performed behavior, with 80% of survey participants choosing not to engage in this activity.

Table 3: Online Behaviors After Participating in Community-Based Tourism
(For those who had experienced community-based tourism)

	Yes		No	
	People	%	People	%
Posting photos/videos on social media	196	85.22	34	14.78
Writing travel reviews and sharing them on travel platforms (Traveloka, etc.)	70	30.43	160	69.57
Writing travel reviews and sharing them on social media (Facebook, Instagram, etc.)	103	44.78	127	55.22
Writing travel reviews and sharing them on Google Maps	52	22.61	178	77.39

Source: Survey results

In terms of online behavior after participating in community-based tourism, for the group of young people who had previously engaged in this type of travel, the following trends were observed: "Posting images/videos on social media" was the most prevalent online behavior, with 85.22% of survey participants having engaged in this activity. Sharing experiential reviews appeared to be less common.

"Writing travel reviews and sharing them on social media (Facebook, Instagram, etc.)" was done by 44.78% of individuals who traveled in the community. "Writing travel reviews and sharing them on travel platforms (Traveloka, etc.)" were practiced by just 30.43% of the surveyed individuals who had participated in community-based tourism. "Writing travel reviews and sharing them on Google Maps" were the least commonly practiced behaviors, with only 22.61% of survey participants opting for this activity. In general, individuals often share their experiences on social media through images and videos, while writing and sharing travel reviews on various platforms are less popular.

4.2.2. For the group yet to participate in community-based tourism

Table 4: Online behaviors before engaging in community-based travel
(For the group that hasn't traveled in this manner but intends to do so in the near future)

	Yes		No	
	People	%	People	%
Reading travel reviews on social media	75	92.59	6	7.41

Reading travel reviews on online forums	67	82.72	14	17.28
Reading travel reviews from blogs	68	83.95	13	16.05
Reading travel reviews from review websites	66	81.48	15	18.52
Searching for travel information on destination websites	75	92.59	6	7.41
Searching for travel information on search engines	73	90.12	8	9.88
Asking or messaging acquaintances and friends about the destination	68	83.95	13	16.05
Contacting service providers	57	70.37	23	28.40
Pre-booking travel products and services	59	72.84	22	27.16
Checking location/weather/traffic information on websites	70	86.42	11	13.58
Seeking travel information from travel agencies' websites	58	71.60	23	28.40
Receiving travel information and promotions via email	44	54.32	37	45.68
Creating travel-related topics on forums	37	45.68	44	54.32

Source: Survey results

In general, 'Reading travel reviews on social media' and 'Searching for travel information on destination websites' are the two most common online behaviors among young individuals with the intention to participate in community-based tourism, both with a percentage of 92.59%. 'Receiving travel information and promoting travel via email' and 'Creating travel-related topics on forums' are the least performed actions, chosen by only 54.32% and 45.68% of survey participants.

4.3. Motivations for participating in community-based tourism

4.3.1. For those who have participated in community-based tourism

Table 5: Motivations for learning when participating in community-based tourism
(For those who have engaged in this form of tourism)

Learning	1	2	3	4	5	Average score	Motivating level	Threshold of recognition
Learning about local culture, traditions, and way of life	17	6	28	98	81	3.96	1	Agree
Exchanging experiences with local residents	11	7	50	103	59	3.83	2	Agree

Learning how to cook local dishes	14	11	55	94	56	3.73	3	Agree
Learning how to make local products	15	12	55	91	57	3.71	4	Agree

Source: Survey results

The majority of young people who have participated in community-based tourism **agree** with the idea of engaging in travel for the purpose of learning, with average scores ranging from 3.71 to 3.96. Among them, the motivation 'Learning about local culture, traditions, and way of life' is the highest with an average score of 3.96.

Table 6: Motivations for spending time with family when participating in community-based tourism
(For those who have engaged in this type of tourism)

Family	1	2	3	4	5	Average score	Motivating level	Threshold of recognition
Spending time with family	20	3	17	72	118	4.15	1	Agree
Nostalgia for childhood memories	15	13	52	76	74	3.79	3	Agree
Visiting friends and family	18	10	37	86	79	3.86	2	Agree

Source: Survey results

Similarly, the majority of young people who have participated in community-based tourism agree that they engage in such travel to spend time with family and friends. Among these motivations, 'Spending time with family' is the most agreed-upon, with an average score of 4.15.

Table 7: Nature-Related Motivations for Participating in Community-Based Tourism
(With those who have experienced this form of travel)

Nature	1	2	3	4	5	Average score	Motivating level	Threshold of recognition
Appreciating the beauty of natural landscapes	17	2	11	79	121	4.24	1	Strongly agree
Experiencing the local weather and atmosphere	14	4	13	86	113	4.22	2	Strongly agree
Engaging in native nature-related activities (camping, hiking...)	14	2	17	86	111	4.21	3	Strongly agree

Source: Survey results

Traveling for nature is the only motivation with a consensus, where all three statements receive '**Strongly Agree**,' and the difference between them is not more than 0.03 points. Among these, the motivation 'To appreciate the beauty of natural landscapes' has the highest agreement with an average score of 4.24.

Table 8: Motivations for experiential exploration when participating in community-based tourism
(With the group that has already engaged in this type of tourism)

Experience Exploration	1	2	3	4	5	Average score	Motivating level	Threshold of Recognition
Gaining more experiences and new adventures	14	2	17	86	111	4.21	2	Strongly agree
To relax and unwind	15	1	12	90	112	4.23	1	Strongly agree
To find new sources of inspiration	15	3	29	88	95	4.07	3	Agree
To escape from a monotonous and hectic lifestyle	14	8	42	78	88	3.95	4	Agree
To create personal value by participating in local life"	17	9	48	71	85	3.86	5	Agree

Source: Survey results

In the group of young people who have already participated in community-based travel, there are 2 motivations in the "Discovery Experience Motivation" category that have a threshold of "**Strongly Agree**," which are "Traveling to relax and unwind" with a score of 4.23 and "Traveling to gain more experiences and new adventures" with a score of 4.21.

4.3.2. For those who have not participated but intend to do so in the near future

Table 9: Learning motivation when participating in community-based travel
(For the group that has not gone but intends to do so in the near future)

Learning	1	2	3	4	5	Average score	Motivating level	Threshold of recognition
To learn about the indigenous culture, traditions, and way of life	3	2	9	45	22	4.00	1	Agree
To exchange experiences with local people	3	3	16	42	17	3.83	2	Agree
To learn how to cook local dishes	3	5	20	34	19	3.75	4	Agree
To learn how to make local products	4	5	15	35	22	3.81	3	Agree

Source: Survey results

The majority of young people who intend to participate in community-based tourism agree with the idea of traveling to learn, with average scores ranging from 3.81 to 4.00. Among them, the motivation "*Learning about local culture, traditions, and lifestyles*" has the highest average score of 4.00.

Table 10: Motivations for spending time with family when participating in community-based tourism
(With the group of those who haven't been but intend to do so in the near future)

Family	1	2	3	4	5	Average score	Motivating level	Threshold of recognition
Spending time with family	5	3	7	30	36	4.10	1	Agree
Nostalgia for childhood memories	3	4	16	37	21	3.85	2	Agree
Visiting friends and family	5	5	18	25	28	3.81	3	Agree

Source: Survey results

Similarly, the majority of Gen Z individuals who intend to participate in community-based tourism agree with the idea of spending time with family. Among these motivations, "*Spending time with family*" is the most agreed-upon motivation with an average score of 4.10. On the other hand, the motivation "*Visiting friends and family*" has the lowest score with 3.81.

Table 11: Motivations for traveling for nature when participating in community-based tourism
(With the group of those who haven't been but intend to do so in the near future).

Nature	1	2	3	4	5	Average score	Motivating level	Threshold of recognition
Appreciating the beauty of natural landscapes	4	1	4	38	34	4.20	1	Agree
Experiencing the local weather and atmosphere	2	3	10	37	29	4.09	3	Agree
Engaging in native nature-related activities (camping, hiking...)	4	2	5	35	35	4.17	2	Agree

Source: Survey results

Traveling for nature is the only motivation among young individuals with the intention to participate in community-based tourism that has an average score above 4 for all motivations. Among these motivations, "*Observing the beauty of natural landscapes*" is the most agreed-upon motivation with an average score of 4.20. The motivation with the lowest average score is "*Experiencing the local weather and atmosphere*" with 4.09 points.

Table 12: Motivations for exploratory experiences when participating in community-based tourism
(With the group of those who haven't been but intend to do so in the near future).

Experience Exploration	1	2	3	4	5	Average score	Motivating level	Threshold of recognition
------------------------	---	---	---	---	---	---------------	------------------	--------------------------

Gaining more experiences and new adventures	3	1	4	41	32	4.21	1	Strongly Agree
To relax and unwind	3	1	6	37	34	4.21	1	Strongly Agree
To find new sources of inspiration	3	1	10	35	32	4.14	3	Agree
To escape from a monotonous and hectic lifestyle	3	2	10	36	30	4.09	4	Agree
To create personal value by participating in local life"	4	3	16	31	27	3.91	5	Agree

Source: Survey results

The motivation to participate in community-based tourism for exploratory experiences is generally highly rated by most Gen Z individuals. All options, except "Creating value for oneself by engaging in local life" (average score of 3.91), have an average score above 4. The motivations "To gain new experiences and explore" and "To relax and unwind" have the highest average score of 4.21.

5. Some Exchanges and Discussion

It can be seen that among the four categories of motivations for participating in community-based tourism among Vietnamese Gen Z young people who have engaged in this type of tourism, the motivation "**Enjoying nature**" is the highest-rated, with an average score of 4.22. It's the only motivation with a "**Strongly Agree**" rating. The other three categories of motivations are all rated as "**Agree**" with an average score of 3.81 or higher. The motivation "**Learning**" has the lowest average score.

Figure 4: Motivations for participating in community-based tourism
(With the group who has already participated in this type of tourism)

Source: Survey results

For young people with the intention to engage in community-based tourism, similar to those who have already participated in this type of tourism, the motivation "**Enjoying nature**" also has the highest average score of 4.15 points. All motivations are recognized as "**Agree**."

Figure 5: Motivations for participating in community-based tourism
(With the group who hasn't participated yet but intends to do so in the near future)

Source: Survey results

There is a significant similarity in the motivations for community-based tourism between the two groups: those who haven't gone yet but have the intention and those who have already participated. The motivation for "Enjoying nature" is the highest and the motivation for "Learning," is the lowest.

For the "**Learning motivation**," both groups' responses fall under the "**Agree**" category. Similarly, the "**Spending time with family motivation**" is perceived as "**Agree**" in both groups. However, there is a difference in the motivation "**Nature**." While the group that has already participated in community-based tourism tends to categorize it as "**Strongly agree**," the other group, who hasn't yet participated but intends to, places it in the "**Agree**" category. This suggests that the appreciation of natural landscapes, weather, local atmospheres, and experiencing local activities might require firsthand experience. This could be considered one of the advantages of community-based tourism in Vietnam. It is essential to promote community-based tourism more extensively to provide detailed information about destinations, emphasizing the enjoyment of space, landscapes, and atmosphere so that young travelers can better understand the values that community-based tourism brings.

As for the "**Experiencing and Exploring motivation**," both survey groups express a similar sentiment. They strongly agree with motivations like "**Traveling for gaining new experiences**" and "**Traveling for relaxation and stress relief**," with all other responses falling under the "**Agree**" category.

There is a significant similarity in online behaviors before participating in community-based tourism among both groups. The most visually striking commonality is the behavior of "**Reading travel reviews on social media**," which is prevalent in both groups. It is conducted by 95.65% of the group that has already participated and 92.59% of the group with the intention to participate. There is a minor difference in the ranking of behaviors between "**Searching for information about travel on destination websites**" and "**Searching for travel information on search engines**." Specifically, "**Searching for information about travel on destination websites**" ranks third in the group that has already participated but second in the group with the intention to participate. Furthermore, in the group that has already participated, **there is a more significant variation in the levels of engagement in these behaviors**. *Online travel is becoming an essential trend in the tourism industry, and Vietnam is considered a country with immense potential in this regard.* Therefore, there is a need to promote the strong application of new technology platforms to create convenience for both domestic and international consumers; Learn from the experiences and skills of leading global companies in online travel, which include aspects such as booking flights, hotel accommodations, and tour packages; Create opportunities for partnerships and collaborations among online travel service providers should be encouraged; Increase interest and support from government agencies for the online travel sector.

6. Conclusion

Community-based tourism is often understood as the involvement of a local community in tourism activities. This initiative typically starts organically in places with scenic attractions and historical sites that attract tourists, and the local population actively participates in serving the needs of travelers. According to a report by Google and Temasek, the scale of online tourism in Vietnam reached 3.5 billion USD in 2018, showing a 15% growth rate. It is estimated that by 2025, this figure will rise to 9 billion USD. Vietnam's tourism market currently ranks fifth

among six countries in the Southeast Asia region, and there is a significant untapped potential, particularly in community-based tourism. The consensus between the government, businesses, and local communities is crucial for the sustainable development of community-based tourism. This form of tourism can significantly contribute to making Vietnam's tourism sector "a true driver of economic growth, spurring the development of various other sectors and contributing to the formation of a modern economic structure"

Author Contributions: All authors contributed to this research.

Funding: Not applicable.

Conflict of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Informed Consent Statement/Ethics Approval: Not applicable.

References

- Beard, J.G.; Ragheb, M.G. (1983). *Measuring Leisure Motivation*. *J. Leis. Res.* (1983), 15, 219–228, doi:10.1080/00222216.1983.11969557.
- Chanapong Arpornpisal (2018). *Tourism Elements Influence the Decision Making in Traveling to Visit Phra Pathom Chedi, Nakhon Pathom, Thailand*. *Asian Administration and Management Review*. Volume 1 Number 1 (January-June 2018)
- Chen CF, Chen FS (2010). *Experience quality, perceived value, satisfaction and behavioral intentions for heritage tourists*. *Tourism Management*. 2010;31(1):29–v. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tourman.2009.02.008>
- Crompton JL (1979). *Motivations for pleasure vacation*. *Annals of Tourism Research*. 1979; 6(4):408–424. Available from: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0160-7383\(79\)90004-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/0160-7383(79)90004-5).
- Dann G. Anomie (1977). *Egoenhancement and tourism*. *Annals of Tourism*. 1977;4(4):184–194. Available from: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0160-7383\(77\)90037-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/0160-7383(77)90037-8).
- Dinh Thuy Dung (2022). What is community-based tourism? Forms, characteristics, and impacts. <https://luatduonggia.vn/>
- Doan Manh Cuong (2019). Developing sustainable community-based tourism (Part 1). <https://vietnamtourism.gov.vn/post/29392>"
- Ec Mahika (2011). *Current trends in tourist motivation*. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/284671490_Current_trends_in_tourist_motivation
- Gnoth, J. (1997). *Tourism Motivation and Expectation Formation*. *Annals of Tourism Research*. 24, 283-304. [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0160-7383\(97\)80002-3](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0160-7383(97)80002-3)
- Greg Richards (2002). *Tourism and Gastronomy*. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/322925141_Tourism_and_Gastronomy
- Fields, D.L. (2002). *Taking the Measure of Work: A Guide to Validated Scales for Organizational Research and Diagnosis*. Sage Publications, Thousand Oaks.
- Ha TTT, et al (2019). Influences of Push and Pull Factors on Tourist Loyalty towards Hoi An Destination. *Hue University Journal of Economics and Development*. 2019;128(5A):147–167. Available from: 10.26459/hueuni-jed.v128i5A.5044.
- Hoteljob.vn (2021). What is community-based tourism? 6 prominent forms of community-based tourism. <https://www.hoteljob.vn/>
- Huy Le (2019). Online tourism is expected to reach 9 billion USD by 2025. <https://vietnamtourism.gov.vn/post/29436>
- Jutamas Phengkonaa & Paithoon Monpanthongb (2022). *Motivation-Based Segmentation and Online Behaviors of Tourists Participating in Community-Based Tourism: A Case Study of Thailand*. *Journal of Multidisciplinary in Social Sciences* (January - April 2022), 18(1): 23-36
- Kim S, Lee C, & Klenosky D (2003). *The influence of push and pull factors at Koreannational parks*. *Tourism Management*. 2003;24:169–180. Available from: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0261-5177\(02\)00059-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0261-5177(02)00059-6)
- Le Thai Phuong, Phan Kim Ngan, Nguyen Thi Bao Nguyen (2022). "Community-Based Tourism Preferences of Young Adults in Da Nang for Local and Nearby Destinations." <http://jst.tnu.edu.vn/jst/article/view/5472/pdf>
- Li M, Zhang H, Xiao H, Chen Y (2015). *A grid-group analysis of tourism motivation*. *International journal of tourism research*. 2015;17(1):35–44. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1002/jtr.1963>.

- Lisa Legault (2016). *Intrinsic and Extrinsic Motivation*.
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/311692691_Intrinsic_and_Extrinsic_Motivation
- Mai TT, et al (2013). "Introduction to Tourism." Hanoi: Labor and Social Affairs.
- Melanie Kay Smith, Ivett Pinke-Sziva, Zombor Berezvai, Karolina Buczkowska-Gołabek (2020). *The changing nature of the cultural tourist: motivations, profiles and experiences of cultural tourists in Budapest*.
<https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/14766825.2021.1898626>
- Miroslav D. Vujicic, James Kennell, Alastair M Morrison, Djordjije Vasiljevic (2020). *Fuzzy Modelling of Tourist Motivation: An Age-Related Model for Sustainable, Multi-Attraction, Urban Destinations*.
https://www.researchgate.net/figure/Tourist-motivations-by-Beard-and-Ragheb-1983_tbl1_344808829
- Ngo Thai Hoang Tuan (2023). Forecasting Trends in the Online Tourism Industry for 2023.
<https://www.brandsvietnam.com/congdong/topic/330604-Du-bao-xu-huong-nganh-du-lich-truc-tuyen-2023>
- Nguyen Thi Hong Ngoc (2017). The Impact of Online Reviews on Tourists' Hotel Selection Decisions in Hue. *Journal of Science, Hue University: Economics and Development*; ISSN 2588–1205. Volume 126, Number 5D, 2017, Pages 41–51; DOI: 10.26459/hueuni-jed.v126i5D.4489
- Nguyen Thi Hoai Dung, Tran Thi Thu Huyen (2023). The Impact of Tour Group Size on the Relationship between Memorable Travel Experiences and Intention to Revisit Domestic Tourist Destinations in Community Tourism in Vietnam. <https://js.ktpt.edu.vn/index.php/jed/article/view/1105>
- Nguyen Thi Thanh Ngan (2023). Exploring Tourist Demand for Community Tourism in Lac Duong District, Lam Dong Province. <http://scholar.dlu.edu.vn/bitstream/>
- Nguyen Thi Van Hanh, Tran Tuyen. Travel Motivations in the Context of Advanced Technology Application. *Journal of Science and Technology Development - Social Sciences and Humanities*, 5(3), 1158-1165
- Peter Johnson and Barry Thomas, eds. (1992). *Perspective on Tourism Policy*. Cassell, P.O. Box C831, Rutherford, NJ 07070. 1992. 240p. <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/004728759203100222>
- Pham Quoc Tri, Trinh Thi Thu (2022). Factors Affecting the Decision to Choose Rural Community-Based Tourism Destinations in the North Central Region. <https://vjol.info.vn/index.php/isscr/article/view/66190>
- Government (2017). Tourism Law. Law No. 09/2017/QH14, dated June 19, 2017.
- Thanh Giang (2019). Developing Online Tourism - A Challenging Game. <https://tapchitaichinh.vn/phat-trien-du-lich-truc-tuyen-cuoc-choi-day-thu-thach.html>
- To Van Hanh, Pham Thi Minh Chinh, Pham Thi Chi (2022). Developing Community-Based Learning Tourism in Hòa Bắc Commune, Hoa Vang District, Da Nang City
<https://ctujsvn.ctu.edu.vn/index.php/ctujsvn/article/view/4430>
- Uysal M, Hagan LR (1993). *Motivation of pleasure to travel and tourism*. In M. A. Khan, M. D. Olsen, & T. Var (Eds.), *VNR'S Encyclopedia of Hospitality and Tourism*. 1993; p. 798– 810.
- Vinperl (2021). Community Tourism: Top 4 Most Attractive Destinations. <https://vinpearl.com>
- Yoon Y, Uysal M (2005). *An examination of the effects of motivation and satisfaction on destination loyalty: a structural model*. *Tourism Management*. 2005;26(1):45–56. Available from: 10.1016/j.tourman.2003.08.016
- Zurina Mohaidin, Koay TZE WEI, Mohsen Murshid (2017). *Factors influencing the tourists' intention to select sustainable tourism destination: a case study of Penang, Malaysia*. *International Journal of Tourism Cities*